

A REVIEW OF TALENT MANAGEMENT TOWARDS FIRM COMPETITIVENESS: FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA FOR ISLAMIC BANKING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This study aims to systematically review the existing studies on the relationship of talent management towards firm competitiveness and suggest opportunities for future research in Islamic banking sector. The study uses systematic literature review (SLR) methods. This study uses articles sourced from the Scopus indexed database. In light of the existing research studies' limitations, this paper suggests that the talent management towards firm competitiveness for Islamic banks still requires more empirical analyses studies using alternative analytical methods and alternative measures. The study provides some implications for research and practice in the field of talent management and firm competitiveness. The study also provides important insights of talent management practices in various industries that can be adapted by Islamic banks across countries. Furthermore, the study helps to determine future research related to talent management in the Islamic banking industry.

Subjects: Business, Management; Human Resource Management

Keywords: Talent management; firm competitiveness; competitive advantage; Islamic banks

Classification codes: M10; M12; O15

1. Introduction

In the 20th century, many business leaders assume that there are at least three important aspects that determine the success of a business competition: financial capital, product & service, and human capital. Among them, human capital appears to be the most precious capital (Jackson, 2014). Human capital plays a key role in increasing worker productivity, providing professional services, and developing the best solutions for the firm based on the knowledge of the company's employees. Employees that have a high level of human capital are more likely to provide consistent and high-quality services, allowing the organization to retain or attract new clients (FarC̃nik & IsteniC̃, 2020). In addition, Muiruri et al. (2021) added that human

capital had a considerable and beneficial influence on firm competitiveness. Talent management is closely related to other human capital functions in the company. So it is necessary to align all human capital functions in the planning process to the implementation of talent management.

Most theories define talent management as a series of integrated human resource processes for identifying, managing, and developing one's abilities based on one's performance with the aim of getting employees who remain in accordance with the work expected by the company. Lewis and Heckman (2006) added that talent management as a comprehensive process that includes recruitment, placement, development, and planning for the betterment of employee development. It demonstrates that talent is something owned by employees who are developed and nurtured by an organization through training and development programs in a long-term process that improves their performance so they can be the driving force behind their contribution to the success of the organization. A company's competitiveness is enhanced by exploiting its best human resources by verifying skills, expertise, and knowledge through competency-based management. When properly managed, human capital can have a substantial impact on an organization's success and ability to compete in the market (Rahmat et al., 2021).

However, talent management has become a critical issue for many organizations all over the world (Bhatnagar 2007). The developments of talent management and a matter of interest for talent strategy has gained attention in the literature in many countries including USA, UK, Japan, India, Australia, China, and through Asia (Yeung 2006; Chugh & Bhatnagar 2006, Dunn 2006; Ruppe 2006; Lewis and Heckman 2006; Bennett and Bell 2004). In addition, talent management has gained much attention in the banking industry, where it has a significant effect towards competitive advantage (Nsour & Tayeh, 2018). Furthermore, talent management is needed by Islamic banks which are still less competitive than conventional banks.

According to a study of Islamic banks transformation in Indonesia, there are number of challenges in managing talent in Islamic banks, including a lack of qualified human resources and a scarcity of individuals capable of mastering a combination between sharia law and finance or banking knowledge (Ascarya & Yumanita, 2009; OJK, 2020; KNEKS, 2021). In addition, there is a gap between the required and available capabilities of talent in the face of technological change, where talents in Islamic banks need to expand their digital technology-related skills (OJK, 2021 & KNEKS, 2021). Therefore, Islamic banks in Indonesia with efficient and effective talent management practices will have significantly outperformed business competition in the four key financial metrics such as net profit margin, return on equity, return on assets, depreciation, taxes, and remuneration (Kamil et al. 2016).

By looking at the above phenomenon, this paper aims to systematically review the existing studies on the relationship of talent management towards firm competitiveness to suggest opportunities for future research in Islamic banking industry. In specific, the research questions of this study are as follows:

RQ1: The degree of gap between academic literature and empirical research on talent management towards firm competitiveness?

RQ2: How does talent management contribute to firm competitiveness?

RQ3: What are the future research agendas in talent management towards firm competitiveness for Islamic banking industry?

The structure of this paper consists of five (5) sections, namely the first section will discuss the background of study together with the objectives, second section will review the literature, third section will present the methodology, fourth section will state the result and analyse the findings, fifth section will summarize the findings and provide recommendations.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Many firms across the globe view talent management as an alternative strategy for attaining a competitive advantage. As a result, firms today are focusing human and organizational capacities on developing a high potential pool of talent as well as nurturing and directing them to ensure the organization's long-term success (Ashif, 2019). Researchers and practitioners have defined talent management (TM) from various perspectives. Talent management (TM) encompasses all the elements of Human Resource Management (HRM) (Lewis, R. E., & Heckman, R. J., 2006). The fundamental relationship between talent management and human resources management is that strategy drives execution. The human resources department and each member of its team must make decisions and act in accordance with the talent management strategy. HRM focuses on all employees in an organization, whereas TM focuses on a select group of pools, people, positions, or practices that add the most value to the firm. (Sparrow et al., 2015; Tarique & Schuler, 2010).

According to Heru (2019), talent management has three (3) main goals: 1) developing high-potential employees, 2) investing in the future of top management, and 3) keeping key personnel. Meanwhile, another study stated that talent management has two roles in a company. First as a value creator, where managers and leaders are expected to create high-quality employees who will be spread throughout the company and cause big changes. Second as a value protector, where those in the human capital management division keep high-credibility employees (Pella & Inayati, 2011). When properly implemented, talent management has the potential to boost an organization's competitive advantage, performance, and productivity.

Figure 1: Talent management as an overarching key process of HRM towards firm competitiveness

Source: modified from Jäger (2009) and Ruël et al. (2013)

According to Jager (2009), TM is an all-encompassing HRM process that encompasses both direct and indirect personnel responsibilities. TM is the direct personnel function, which may be considered as both an HR function and the direct executive function of a line manager. The strategic management of human resources is an indirect function. Each factor has an effect on the TM processes. Consequently, it is essential to know that TM cannot be divorced from the business plan of the company (Guthridge, Komm, & Lawson, 2006). TM is a component of both the HRM strategy and the business strategy. The TM strategy of a corporation must align with their business strategy.

To understand TM, the following five steps of the TM process must be explained:

1. **Talent attraction:** Companies strive to represent themselves as brands that inspire customer and employee confidence and loyalty. A company's ability to achieve both strong economic and strong operational results, to offer competitive compensation and personal incentives that provide value to employees, and to have a strong brand image are all crucial factors for attracting talent.
2. **Talent identification and capture:** This phase requires an initial analysis of the talent of the company's key positions and an examination of the potential supply and future demand associated with the company's expansion plans. Typically, companies use performance and employee potential evaluations to identify talented employees. (Jiménez et al., 2008) found that integrating potential assessment and performance assessment is a powerful tool for identifying talent.
3. **Talent development:** This phase is characterized by the company's efforts to develop its employees professionally in order to enhance organizational performance (Den Hartog et al., 2004; Hatum, 2010). This includes training required for a higher position or a change

in activity to increase the knowledge of the workforce. Therefore, individualized development plans tailored to the needs of the employee and the organization are desirable. (Jiménez et al., 2008) Talent development promotes employee mobility, either within the same area or from one area to another, and between different departmental units.

4. **Talent Engagement:** This phase in which the organization builds talent engagement through employee dialogue as a central leadership culture instrument (Bhatnagar, 2008). Facilitate communication between employees and their supervisors at the outset of the evaluation period, so that roles and expected levels of performance are clear.
5. **Talent retention:** This phase typically entails the formulation of a salary and personal incentive policy linked to the generation of commitment and motivation, thereby facilitating the forging of a strong relationship between the employer and the employee (Rynes et al., 2005). Some examples of these initiatives include the creation of personalized career plans, the development of an internal brand, and policies that promote flexibility and help employees balance their personal and professional lives (Jiménez et al., 2008).

As a result, it is possible to conclude that a company's talent management might vary over time, reflecting its dynamic character (Krishnan and Scullion, 2017). Organizations may modify their talent management practices over time in response to changes in the internal and external circumstances (Thunnissen, 2016; Thunnissen & Gallardo-Gallardo, 2017). This illustrates how flexible and complex talent management is in use. To conclude, strategic human resources management as an indirect HR function, talent management process, and talent management as HR function and direct executive function of line manager lead to firm competitiveness.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

In order to achieve the objective, this research used the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) as a suitable method to identify the findings of previous scholars to specific research questions (Gough & Richardson, 2018). SLR is defined by Fink (2019) as a systematic, explicit, and reproducible approach for locating, analyzing, and synthesizing the current corpus of finished and recorded work created by researchers, academics, and practitioners. This method also has been widely used for management research because it offers a transparent, reproducible, and iterative review process (Kaliannan et al., 2022; Tarique & Schuler, 2010; McDonnell et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Gough & Richardson (2018) identify that systematic literature reviews are grounded on a set of common principles which are guided by a research question and systematic approaches.

3.1 Information sources and period

The systematic literature review was conducted for the relevant articles on Scopus published journals during the period 2010–2021 in English. The rationale for the year 2010 selection to start the review is to ensure reviewing most of the related literature. Related key terms such as talent management (TM), firm competitiveness, competitive advantage which are similar concepts were used to conduct the search.

3.2 Search strategy

Related key phrases like Talent Management and Firm Competitiveness were used to do the search. The authors used Boolean search OR to combine the two keywords, such as "Talent Management" for the independent variable and "Firm Competitiveness or Competitive Advantage" for the dependent variable, in the search field. They chose papers that contained these keywords in at least one of the following fields: title, abstract, and keywords.

Figure 2: Data Collection and Analysis Process

There are five phases to the actual procedure for gathering and analyzing data. In the first step, 958 articles from the three databases (Emerald, ProQuest, and Sciedirect) were chosen after the results were filtered using a Boolean search OR based on their relevance to the objectives of this study using relevant keywords. There were 441 papers in total after the duplicates were removed in step two. Third, 38 publications were obtained from full-text articles that were evaluated for eligibility and stored material according to their respective keywords. Forth, the collected papers' contents also were fully reviewed, and only the papers that highlighted the relationship between talent management and firm competitiveness were selected for the final literature analysis which resulted in 13 papers consisting of 7 papers are theoretical while 6 are empirical studies. Figure 2. Provides a summary of the 4 (four) steps mentioned that explain data collection and literature search process.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This study employs a descriptive analysis to systematically review the talent management and firm competitiveness based on a variety of empirical and theoretical studies that can provide a deeper understanding. Due to limited previous studies that discussed talent management and firm competitiveness, this study found that there is a large gap between theoretical and empirical studies that need to be explored by future research.

Moreover, the 13 research articles selected come from 13 different journals indexed by Scopus database from diversified fields such as human resource management, talent management, competitive advantage, firm competitiveness, and organizational performance which emphasizes the diverse characteristics of the subject. Out of the 13 articles, 7 articles are theoretical while 6 are empirical studies. Table I. summarized the final papers collection based on authors, nature of studies, and journals.

Table 1: Summary of the final articles collection

No.	Authors and Year of Publication	Nature of The Study		Journals indexed by Scopus	
		Empirical	Theoretical	Journal Name	Quartiles/ H-Index
1	Aljbour, A., French, E., & Ali, M. (2021)	-	✓	International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management	Q2/61
2	Sivathanu, B., & Pillai, R. (2019)	✓	-	International Journal of Organizational Analysis	Q2/25
3	Shet, S. V. (2020)	-	✓	Human Resource Development International	Q2/49
4	Schreuder, R., & Noorman, S. (2019)	-	✓	Development and Learning in Organizations	Q3/15
5	Sivathanu, B., & Pillai, R. (2019)	✓	-	International Journal of Socio technology and Knowledge Development	Q3/10
6	Kabwe, C., & Okorie, C. (2019)	✓	-	Thunderbird International Business Review	Q1/37
7	Claus, L. (2019)	-	✓	BRQ Business Research Quarterly	Q1/26
8	Glaister, A. J., Karacay, G., Demirbag, M., & Tatoglu, E. (2018)	✓	-	Human Resource Management Journal	Q1/77
9	Ganaie, M. U., & Haque, M. I. (2017)	-	✓	Academy of Strategic Management Journal	Q3/17
10	N'Cho, J. (2017)	✓	-	Procedia Computer Science	Q3/76
11	Shah, N., Irani, Z., & Sharif, A. M. (2017)	✓	-	Journal of Business Research	Q1/195
12	Martin, A. (2015)	-	✓	International Journal of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Q3/3
13	Cheese, P. (2010)	-	✓	Human Resource Management International Digest	Q4/12

4.1 Theoretical Studies on the Talent Management towards Firm Competitiveness

Some final collection of research articles from journals indexed in Scopus shows that there are at least seven (7) theoretical studies that explain why talent management is important for firm competitiveness.

According to research undertaken by Claus (2019) on the topic of human resource disruption, it is necessary to reinvent talent management. The findings showed that forward-thinking businesses across industries have come to the conclusion that current talent management strategies are falling short of employees' expectations as a result of rapid demographic, technological, and global shifts. In addition, modern experts in people management are building out what is called a "HR stack," which comprises additional management frameworks including design thinking, agile management, behavioral economics, and HR analytics.

The existing body of knowledge in talent management also has to be expanded in order to accommodate new information and abilities from management-related disciplines outside of HR (both the traditional transactional HR expertise and the more strategic HR talent management professional knowledge). In the meantime, until enterprises broaden the talent management dialogue, they will not be able to sustainably reinvent their present personnel management methods. In addition, a new dialogue about talent management is developing, with an emphasis on societal interventions, shared accountability, and cooperation between different tiers of workers, businesses, and the public. Consequently, forward-thinking businesses are currently implementing an enhanced HR stack.

Ganaie and Haque (2017) also did a study to help people understand human talent management better from a theoretical and conceptual point of view. To do this, they came up with a conceptual framework and a few propositions to explain how competency focus, talent pooling, talent investment, and talent orientation all play a role in creating value. The study showed that a firm's approach to talent management may also have an effect on how competitive it is and how well it does its job. Also, this model might help practitioners find the most important part of the talent management process and improve their focus on creating more value for a company. This model may also help practitioners align their talent strategies with their business strategies in a way that gives their businesses more value (shareholders, employees, owners, customers, agents, and other stakeholders).

Another study on the evidence-based multilevel framework of talent management was done by Aljbour, French, and Ali (2021). The multilevel framework suggests that talent management perspectives affect talent management practices, which in turn affect the outcomes for the organization, the group, and the individual. The results show that a mix of inclusive and exclusive perspectives creates a hybrid approach that can be used in a variety of talent management practices. In addition, the 67 studies that looked at the results of talent management found that organizational performance was the most noticeable result.

However, Cheese (2010) investigated the lessons learned from the recession and where it should direct the attention going forward in talent management for the new era. Findings from the study suggest that businesses can improve their responsiveness and effectiveness by speeding up the adoption of new business models and methods of operation. Things like more malleable employment models and flexible working arrangements, as well as the growing tendency of "virtualization" of work (doing work remotely from different locations or countries but as part of the same team or process). In addition, the study's findings suggest that one of the most important areas for managers of all levels is developing their core leadership capabilities in order to better manage people, especially in the context of a more diverse workforce, as well as to manage change, deal with uncertainty, and capitalize on opportunities to align and engage their teams as a result.

Shet (2020) did another study in the same area to look at the modern issues of strategic talent management (STM) in an international setting. The goal of the study is to address the challenges in the field of strategic talent management from the stakeholders' point of view and to help build the needed knowledge in the field of STM from a global perspective. It talks about

the different approaches to STM, such as the resource-based view (RBV), managing expert talent, supply chain approach to talent management, employer branding and career management, typology of management strategies, and globalizing the HR Architecture.

Martin (2015) also did a study on the role of talent management in getting a workforce ready to be agile. The study showed that organizations that know how important it is to have a talented, flexible workforce will be able to stay in business and be successful in the long run. Through the "Succession Planning" process, an organization can also effectively handle changes in the current workforce, predict and plan for future human capital needs, such as when the organization grows, and build a talent-agile culture to lead the way. Also, succession planning is usually done in five major steps: 1) find the most important positions in the workforce; 2) find the skills needed for each position; 3) find strategies for managing succession; 4) write down and carry out the plan; and 5) evaluate the plan. This cycle keeps going as the organizations grow, change, and move to new places. The main goal of talent strategies is to find, hire, train, and keep good employees. To measure the return on investment (ROI) and effectiveness of the processes and programs put in place, key performance indicators or metrics must be chosen.

In addition, Schreuder and Noorman (2019) investigated the role of strategic talent management in the creation of strategic value by placing top talent in important roles. Traditional people management techniques cannot lead to organizational success, according to the report. Additionally, the study assesses prevalent personnel management approaches and demonstrates the necessity for an alternative approach. In addition, the study indicates that strategic talent management should link and mutually support business development and personal development in order to increase strategic success. In addition, the study proposes the novel notion of A-level jobs in which top talents and strategic organizational competencies can mutually strengthen one another.

4.2 Empirical Studies on the Talent Management towards Firm Competitiveness

There are at least six (6) empirical studies providing empirical support for talent management's contribution to firm competitiveness.

Glaister et al. (2018) study the relationship between human resource management (HRM) practices, talent management (TM), and firm performance. In addition, their study explores the role of HRM/business strategy alignment in the context of emerging markets using survey data from 198 enterprises in Turkey. Resource-based view (RBV) and dynamic capabilities were utilized to analyze the relationship between HRM practices, TM practices, and company performance, as well as the moderating effect of HRM and business strategy alignment in an emerging market. The study demonstrates that TM is a crucial transmission mechanism mediating the relationship between HRM and company performance when focused on a set of actions targeted at establishing labor networks and social capital. Lastly, the study found that alignment between HRM strategy and business strategy boosts these performance consequences but is not a necessary component of the HRM-TM performance relationship.

Kabwe & Okorie (2019) conduct another study on the effectiveness of talent management in international companies. The study contributes to the body of knowledge by qualitatively assessing managerial experiences of TM practices in 17 European multinational corporations with between 800 and 200,000 employees. To be more competitive, this study emphasizes the need for companies to develop their human resources as an important asset. The study also argues that if TM is applied correctly, it can result in the creation of specialized competencies that can alleviate the pressures of cross-border business difficulties and contribute to a durable competitive advantage.

Sivathanu & Pillai (2019) evaluated the existing literature and conducted semi-structured interviews with 125 HR managers from global organizations in India to investigate the impact of technology on talent management for organizational performance. The results show that the use of technology for talent management can improve organizational performance. In addition, the study also stresses the importance of talent metrics and analytics and HR business alliances.

In another study, Sivathanu and Pillai (2019) conduct an additional empirical study in the same context, which focuses on the role of technology and talent analytics for talent management as a game changer for organizational performance. The impact of HR tech on business outcomes is analyzed in this study. Additionally, 122 senior HR officials from Indian-based and international corporations were interviewed using a grounded theory technique and semi-structured questions. This research revealed that technology usage for talent management aids in talent analytics and strategic HR management (SHRM). Moreover, the study discovered that talent analytics and SHRM result in the creation of a high-performing talent pool, which boosts business results. N'Cho (2017) investigated the possible advantages of talent analytics. According to the research, businesses can improve their talent management with the help of talent analytics by doing the following: identifying the best HR, selecting the best talent based on the requirements of each project phase, gathering and analyzing information to attract millennials, defining the right time and the right way to develop talent while complying with the department's needs, and redeploying talent across the project phases as needed to meet emerging challenges.

Shah, Irani, and Sharif (2017) conducted a second study to highlight the contextual application of big data in a human resource case study, which can be accomplished through the development of a normative conceptual model that seeks to encompass employee behaviors and attitudes in the context of organizational change readiness. A data sample from the huge public sector organization was utilized by the researcher. In addition, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used in this study to determine the income, job advancement, organizational loyalty, and organizational identity factors that influence employee job satisfaction. The research presented in this paper has also offered empirical evidence demonstrating how economic rewards and intrinsic happiness can increase significant and favorable employee attitudes and behaviors toward organizational change. The study hypothesizes that employees' support for change would rise as their sense of attachment and quality of relationship with the firm improve. In conclusion, the study suggests that organization management should focus on both attitude and behavior elements in order to

favorably influence employee attachment in terms of willingness and desire to continue membership during organizational transition.

4.3 Recommendation for Future Research in Islamic Banking Industry

Talent management is viewed as a strategy that consists of all elements of human resource management starting from recruitment to retention. In brief, the five fundamental functions of human resource management are staffing, development, remuneration, safety and health, and employee and labor relations. The process of talent management includes talent attraction, talent identification, talent development, talent engagement, and talent retention which put all members of the organization to have a similar vision towards competitiveness. On the other hand, the discussion of talent management in Islamic banking industry is still limited. With the emergence of digitalisation, an organization has to be able to adapt with the new digital technology, such as blockchain, internet of things, big data, and machine learning, while the talent management strategy has to follow the changes in the industry.

In light of this discussion, there are some important points that can be recommended for future research on talent management towards firm competitiveness of Islamic banks studies, specifically competitiveness during the digital disruption era. The following are some research directions for future research:

1. What are the factors that influence talent management toward the firm competitiveness of Islamic banks?
2. What are the criteria of talent measurement in order to increase the competitiveness of Islamic banks?
3. How to design an ideal talent management system model in increasing the competitiveness of Islamic banks?
4. How to evaluate the performance of the talent management system in increasing the competitiveness of Islamic banks?
5. How to formulate strategic priorities for the talent management system in increasing the competitiveness of Islamic banks?

Furthermore, future research is encouraged to use alternative analytical methods and alternative measures, such as SEM (structural equation modeling), SSM (soft system methodology), scenario planning, fuzzy AHP (analytical hierarchy process).

5. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study is to systematically review the literature related to talent management and competitiveness. In particular, the study critically analysed the theoretical and empirical findings of previous studies that would lead to further analysis of the impact of talent management on firm competitiveness in Islamic banks. Talent management theories have been based on the philosophy that recognizing and nurturing employees' talents would result

in long-term competitive returns for the organization, while empirical studies in talent management shows that talent management has a significant impact on firm competitiveness.

In order to improve the firm competitiveness, companies should develop better strategies that fulfill the need to be agile and responsive in the market, such as identify the best HR, select the best talent, define the right strategy to develop talent, and redeploy talent across the project phases. TM programs, activities, policies, and practices are all ways that people can be managed to give a company a competitive advantage. So, Islamic banking managers and employees can change, accept, and use its practices as part of their daily work. It's well known that the banking industry is both changing and competitive, so innovative TM practices should focus on giving employees new and different skills and knowledge to make sure they can adapt to change. By looking at the gap between theoretical and empirical, this study provides five future research questions that guide the researcher to have more meaningful research.

6. IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

The study provides some implications for research and practice in the field of talent management and firm competitiveness. Although there are numerous studies on talent management, research on the role of talent management towards firm competitiveness is extremely limited, particularly in the Islamic banking industry. Thus, the analysis undertaken in this paper aims to address the literature gaps on talent management towards firm competitiveness of Islamic Banks and the important practical issues of talent management in Islamic banks. Therefore, the study serves as a guide for academicians, researchers, management of Islamic Banks, Islamic banks practitioners, regulatory authorities, e.g. financial services authority (OJK) and central banks, related authorities, e.g. National Committee for Islamic Economy and Finance (KNEKS), and Islamic international autonomous non-for-profit organizations, e.g. AAOIFI and the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB).

This study reviews the existing literature on the relationship of talent management toward firm competitiveness as recommendation practice for Islamic banking industry. The authors suggested that there is an important literature gap that still needs to be filled, such as the talent management model and strategy for Islamic banking industry. Besides that, the study also provides important insights of talent management practices in various industries that can be adapted for Islamic banks across countries. Furthermore, the study gives important summary for various stakeholders such as management of Islamic banks, policy makers, and related authorities across countries to understand how to enhance the Islamic bank competitiveness through talent management system and practice.

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